

Decision Tree Creation with Novel Componendo and Dividendo Split Attribute Technique

*¹Cheruku Sudarsana Reddy
 Research Scholar
 Department of Computer Science and Engineering
 AcharyaNagarjuna University (ANU), Guntur (Dist)
 Andhra Pradesh, India.

Dr.O.Nagaraju
 BOS Chairman-UG
 Computer Science, ANU
 APRDC
 Nagarjunasagar-522439

ABSTRACT: Decision tree classifier models are considered to be the fundamental components in the landscape of machine learning, data mining, and many other advanced learning techniques, offering intuitive and powerful solutions for both classification and regression problems. This particular research paper provides some important exploration details of decision tree classifier models such as C4.5 and classification and regression trees (CART), which actually laid down the strong groundwork foundation for high interpretability and rule based learning. These potential methods are analysed in terms of their splitting criteria, pruning strategies and handling of categorical and continuous attributes. Further this research paper explores ensemble learning such as random forest models, which significantly enhance predictive accuracy and robustness by aggregating multiple decision tree classifier models that use bagging and boosting techniques. XGBOOST classifier model is advanced gradient boosting model having high scalability, comprehensibility, superior performance in high dimensional datasets. Selecting good optimal or suboptimal split attribute is the fundamental criterion in any decision tree learning. A new split attribute technique, called Componendo and Dividendo (CAD-rule), is proposed in this research paper and it is evaluated by employing many UCI machine learning datasets. The experimental results have shown that the superiority of the proposed split attribute technique.

Key Words:C4.5, CART, random forests, XGBoost, Componendo and Dividendo, CAD-rule, Employee_Dataset
 Secondary key words: Gini Index, CHAID,balanced partition, Tsallais

I. INTRODUCTION

Decision tree classifier models are among the most extensively used and effective tools in supervised machine learning domain and these tools are valued due to their simplicity, interpretability, and having the ability to model complex, non-linear relationships. These special algorithms operate by recursively splitting data in the internal nodes of the decision tree. C4.5 decision tree algorithm is developed by Quinlan, and C4.5 is an extension of ID3 decision tree algorithm. ID3 uses continuous attributes, pruning technique and information gain ratio as its splitting criterion. In parallel, classification and regression trees (CART) were proposed by Breiman and CARTs have many desirable features such as binary trees, use Gini impurity function or mean squared error as splitting criterion. To overcome instability and over fitting problems ensemble techniques such as random forests are proposed. Random forests construct multiple decision tree classifier models, and outputs of these individual decision trees are aggregated to increase the generalization performance and robustness. In recent times advanced techniques such as Extreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost) have emerged with salient features, optimized decision tree construction, parallel processing, and the ability to handle large scale and high-dimensional datasets.

The very first algorithm ID3 uses Shannon entropy technique to measure information gain value. C4.5 is one of the best decision tree classifier algorithms and it uses information gain ratio technique to determine the best split attribute using entropy measure. Mathematical formula for entropy measure is

$$\text{Info}(D) = - \sum_{i=1}^{i=m} p_i \log_2(p_i) \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

Where D is the dataset and m represents distinct number of classes in the dataset.

Classification and regression trees (CARTs) split attribute formula is Gini Index and it measures the impurity of the dataset, D, as

$$\text{Gini}(D) = 1 - \sum_{i=1}^{i=m} p_i^2 \dots \dots \dots (2)$$

The Gini index considers only a binary split for each attribute.

Tsallis entropy quantity is defined as

$$S_q(p_i) = k \cdot \frac{1}{q-1} \left(1 - \sum_i p_i^q \right) \dots \dots \dots (3)$$

Where q is a real parameter called electronics-index, and k is a positive constant.

Decision trees are used in many varieties of applications including many real time practical applications; in this research paper, decision trees are closely analyzed and interpreted in a convenient way and in particular ID3 algorithm is thoroughly analyzed and explained in detail [1]. ID3 uses entropy based metric for determining optimal, sub-optimal or the best split attribute. Advantages and disadvantages are clearly analyzed and discussed in detail. Decision trees are corner stones in machine learning and these well-organized decision trees are predominantly being used in many real applications; this paper particularly explains in detail about all the existing decision tree algorithms [2]. XGBoost technique is scalable, ensemble and an efficient boosting algorithm useful for data classification [3]; the research work in this paper proposes algorithm details based on parameters like generalization performance, training speed, and some other parameter settings. Three major algorithms namely-XGBoost, random forest and gradient boosting are compared thoroughly. After thorough analysis, observation and understanding the results it is concluded that XGBoost is not necessarily the best choice under all possible circumstances.

Current decision trees can handle only fixed data but not special data types such as trees, graphs, sequences and images and so on; one way to handle sequence data is first it is converted into vector data and then existing techniques are applied for managing sequences effectively; another technique is usage of special algorithms that can handle sequence directly [4]. Decision tree model represents a set of rules after learning and rule learning approaches are categorized two types; the first one is called divide and conquer and the second one is called separate and conquer[5]. The first one is also known as top-down-induction of decision tree classifier models and the second one is also known as covering technique. A new algorithm is proposed based on the Gini-index split attribute technique.

Splitting technique is an important part of the decision tree learning in both machine learning and data mining. It is a well-known fact that there is no single split attribute technique that always will give the best performance for all the selected real time problems. In this research paper exploration of relative performance of two families is carried out [6]; the first family is called conditional entropy family and the second family that is based on the class-attribute mutual information.

A new split attribute approach is proposed for decision tree learning [7] and this new technique is structurally very good for obtaining high classification results. Chi-square split attribute technique algorithm is used in CHAID decision tree algorithm [8]; this criterion generally tends to in favor of the attributes with more values. Authors have invented a new algorithm to overcome this problem. Gain, gain ratio, Gini index are special cases of Tsallis splitting criterion in the process of decision tree construction [9]; Tsallis technique is highly generalizable technique that contains a new parameter, q , which is performance adjustable quantity. Tsallis actually implemented as a general way of representing Shannon entropy, gain ratio and Gini index. Decision tree tools are predominantly used for stream data mining; in this paper authors have addressed and developed a family of new split attribute techniques for data classification in stationary data streams [10]. More importantly two hybrid splitting criterion is also proposed.

Creativity and Originality of the Research Work:

Since it was not present in any of the previous research efforts, the new data split technique suggested in this paper is entirely original. The computing burden of the proposed split rule is straightforward yet distinct for numerical and categorical qualities. This paper's study is unquestionably very innovative, thorough, efficient, and successful.

Quality of the proposed work presentation: The proposed work covers a wide range of real-time business applications in addition to numerous scientific ones, such as medical diagnosis, scientific research, retail, business, agriculture, banking, and the military. It is also scalable, simple, quick, efficient, and effective. It is provided in a way that is simple to comprehend. It would be ideal to minimize the model's training and cost as much as possible. The recommended work is of a good quality and is presented in an understandable way using a simple example training dataset, allowing readers who are not familiar with the subject to grasp it.

Relevance and Timeliness: There are no issues with applying the suggested work, which can be used in a variety of real-time applications. Additionally, time limits do not apply, with the exception of extremely large training datasets.

Technical content and scientific rigour: technical content is simple and it is clearly presented with an example. Sufficient numbers of real time experiments are conducted for model accuracy determination. Test datasets are available for finding testing accuracy of the proposed model. Technically speaking the existing data split rules are highly enriched and high bench mark standards are established.

Results: Using numerous UCI machine learning datasets, experimental results are presented in an easy-to-understand manner. Training and testing sets of UCI machine learning datasets are separated. In this case, class label counts are calculated from the training dataset without the need for a training step. Model accuracy is determined using the test dataset. This concept undoubtedly raises the legitimacy and generalizability of the suggested method. UCI machine learning datasets are used during experimentation to provide adequate evidence of empirical validation.

The rest of the present research paper is systematically organized as follows: The required literature details are presented in the section-2, actual problem definition is presented in the section-3, actual proposed framework and corresponding algorithm is

presented in the section-4, and experimental results are presented in the section-5. The paper ends with some concluding remarks in section 6.

2. EXISTING LITERATURE SURVEY

Authors proposed a new split rule in decision tree learning using an excellent mathematical formula. The research study in [11], Authors proposed a novel method for directly predicting the class label of unseen test tuples based on intelligent mathematical formulas. Many machine learning researchers and industry experts [12] will benefit from this paper's thorough overview of decision trees, which cover their fundamental ideas, applications and algorithms. Advanced decision tree based research applications were mainly concentrated and being implemented in medical diagnosis and fraud detections. In this paper [13] authors have focused on evasion attacks against decision tree ensembles and a new algorithm was proposed on the basis of a formal threat model. In this research paper [14] authors have proposed new decision tree learning algorithms with new node splitting techniques with parameterized classes of node splitting, the proposed study also explores pruning strategies to balance accuracy and interpretability.

Previous decision tree classifiers are unable to provide accurate representations of classification accuracies and decision tree sizes. A novel algorithm is proposed [15] for learning optimal classification trees, which are created, based on dynamic programming technique having ability to globally optimize the decision trees. This research work introduces a non-greedy algorithm [16] which optimizes data split rules and leaf parameters across all tree levels. Authors have experimentally proved that proposed decision trees have produced superior performance when compared with traditional decision trees.

This paper proposes an algorithm for classifying non-linear data by combining decision trees and neural network models [17], also, experiments are conducted employing various datasets; the results have shown that superiority of the proposed technique. This research work explores the automated design of decision tree algorithms by using evolution algorithms based on optimized decision tree induction strategies [18]. A new algorithm called multi-relational decision tree learning is proposed [19], which automatically extends existing decision tree classifiers to handle complex relational structures. A new algorithm is proposed for improving personalization in student academic performance [20] which includes dynamic tests with a predictive model. Sequence data modelling is important particularly in medical diagnosis [21]; existing decision tree classifiers can handle structured data only but not unstructured data such as trees and graphs. Authors have proposed a new algorithm for efficient management of sequence datasets. A new algorithm is proposed for effectively exploiting the feedback loop originated from the internals of any ensemble decision trees [22]; the proposed algorithm brings back correctly all the perturbations.

Traditional decision trees are in capable of processing uncertain data; there is a need to handle such uncertain data using decision tree classifiers [23]; a new algorithm is proposed for handling uncertainty in datasets using probability density functions. Privacy preservation of data is important in many domains [24]; in the present paper, privacy preserving techniques are applied using decision trees. The proposed algorithm is directly applicable to datasets for converting privacy preserving datasets. New algorithm is proposed using ensemble decision trees – naïve decision tree classifiers and if-else decision trees for handling memory locality issues [25]; experimental based time complexities are calculated for various realizations of decision trees. Proposed optimized memory layout achieves a reduction in execution time.

Split attribute techniques are analysed in detail, six decision tree algorithms corresponding to six split attribute techniques are closely observed and analysed. Splitting techniques are compared using four different metrics such as information theory, distance based theory, statistical based criteria, and other criteria. Decision tree accuracy, depth, internal nodes, size and time complexity are employed for comparison purpose. Various decision trees are developed using different types of split attribute techniques. In this paper [26], six different split attribute techniques are compared using multiple parameters such classification accuracy, decision tree size, height, leaf nodes and so on. Earlier research persons have observed and noticed that ID3, C4.5 and CART are reasonably good in performance. Model understanding is important for making accurate decisions. Additive models such as gradient boosting and some interaction models have been already investigated individually. A new decision tree called additive decision tree is proposed in this paper and this model is experimentally verified and found that the results are equivalent to gradient boosting results [27]. It is a well-known fact that ensemble learning is one of the effective strategies for improving the generalization capability of the decision tree; in this paper fusing principle and attribute reduction techniques are proposed for generalization improvement [28]. A new technique was proposed for constructing decision trees without using any training data using large language models and only LLM based operations [29]; despite not using of any selected training data but decision trees are well qualified in producing high performance experimental results.

3. PROBLEM DEFINITION

During decision tree learning, determining the optimal split attribute is crucial. Traditional decision tree classifier models are ID3, C4.5 and CART, whereas advanced decision trees are XGBoost, CNN, RNN and other type of novel decision trees based large language models such as generative pre-trained transformer (GPT). Numerous research specialist experts are conducting ongoing research studies on decision tree learning quality improvements. The research study in this paper particularly focuses and proposes a sophisticated split attribute technique called Componendo and Dividendo (CAD-rule) split rule for smooth, efficient and effective decision tree learning.

4. METHODOLOGY OF PROPOSED COMPONENTO AND DIVIDENDO SPLIT ATTRIBUTE TECHNIQUE

In decision tree learning tuples in the dataset are separated into distinct partitions for each possible split attribute, and for each potential split attribute the aggregate split attribute score value is calculated, after calculating the maximum class label count (x_i) and minimum class label count (y_i) for each separate partition. During decision tree creation, the best possible split attribute is determined by taking the probable split attribute with the highest computed aggregate split score. Important point is that categorical attribute values are divided into many partitions whereas numerical attribute values are divided into only two partitions. Two partitions are possible for continuous (numerical) attributes whereas more than two partitions are possible for categorical (discrete) attributes. Finally the attribute with highest split attribute score is selected for data split.

For example, course is a categorical attribute with $n=6$ distinct values (Ph.D, M.S, M.Tech, B.Tech, M.Sc, MBA) then values of course attribute are separated into $n=6$ partitions and aggregate score is determined using the mathematical formula:

$$\text{Aggregate score of (course)} = \frac{x_1 - y_1}{x_1 + y_1} + \frac{x_2 - y_2}{x_2 + y_2} + \dots + \frac{x_n - y_n}{x_n + y_n} = \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{x_i - y_i}{x_i + y_i} \dots \dots \dots (4)$$

This formula tells how discriminative the course attribute is with respect to the class labels given in the dataset.

Values of numerical attribute are divided into only two partitions, left partition and right partition using mathematical formula:

$$\text{Aggregate score of (numerical attribute)} = \frac{x_1 - y_1}{x_1 + y_1} + \frac{x_2 - y_2}{x_2 + y_2} = \sum_{i=1}^2 \frac{x_i - y_i}{x_i + y_i} \dots \dots \dots (5)$$

Proposed mathematical formulas are used to evaluate the discriminative power of an attribute. Numerator tells the strength of the partition whereas the denominator tells the normalization factor of the partition.

Here how aggregate scores are calculated for the categorical and numerical attributes is the main highlight point during decision tree learning. Suppose the course categorical attribute has $n = 6$ distinct categorical values (Ph.D, M.S, M.Tech, B.Tech, M.Sc, M.B.A) and for each categorical value a separate partition is created, say for example, x_i is the highest count of a particular class label in the partition one and y_i is the smallest count of some other class label in the same partition one. Here, x_i represents number of instances of highest class label count of a particular class label in the i^{th} partition; and y_i represents number of instances of lowest class label count of some other class label in the same i^{th} partition of the attribute. Binary splits are applicable for numerical attributes, and data is divided into left partition and right partition. For the left partition, difference of highest class label count and lowest class label count is computed and this difference is divided by the sum of maximum class label count and minimum class label count to get the relative difference score of that particular partition; similarly for the right partition difference is computed and divided by sum of maximum and minimum class label counts to get relative difference score of the right partition, finally both left and right relative difference quantities are summed up to get final aggregate score of the selected split attribute.

Componento and dividendo formula is used in attribute evaluation process, often in data classification problems to measure how likely an attribute can distinguish between different classes (major class and minor class). The numerator ($x_i - y_i$) measures the imbalance between the largest and smallest class label counts in the i^{th} partition and it is called the strength or bias of that partition; the denominator $x_i + y_i$ is a normalization factor of the i^{th} partition of a particular attribute. This normalization factor avoids bias from partitions with more data. A high aggregate score of a particular attribute means actually the attribute is more informative for data classification.

- 1) x_i represents highest class label count of the i^{th} partition.
- 2) y_i represents lowest class label count of the same i^{th} partition.
- 3) $x_i - y_i$ represents individual strength of the i^{th} partition and this formula measures the imbalance between the largest and smallest class label counts in the i^{th} partition.
- 4) $x_i + y_i$ is a normalization factor of the i^{th} partition of a particular attribute.
- 5) $\frac{x_i - y_i}{x_i + y_i}$ is aggregate score of an i^{th} individual partition of any attribute
- 6) $\sum_{i=1}^n \frac{x_i - y_i}{x_i + y_i}$ aggregate score of an individually selected categorical attribute
- 7) $\frac{x_1 - y_1}{x_1 + y_1} + \frac{x_2 - y_2}{x_2 + y_2}$ aggregate score of selected numerical attribute.

4.1 DECISION TREE ALGORITHM

Algorithm-1 Decision_Tree_Componento_and_Dividendo(Tree root, D)

Input: D, Training dataset

Output: Decision Tree Classifier Model

- 1: create root node and at the same time enter training dataset, D, into the root node
- 2: root = Create_Decision_Tree_Componento_and_Dividendo(root, D)
- 3: return root

Algorithm-2 Create_Decision_Tree_Componendo_and_Dividendo(root, D)

1: find the homogeneity of the current node
 2:if all tuples in the root node have the same class label then
 3: convert the current node into the leaf node
 4: return root
 5:if the attribute list is empty then
 6: convert the current node into the leaf node and return
 7: end if
 8:split_attribute = Find_Good_Split_Attribute_Componendo_and_Dividendo(root, D)
 9: divide data into partitions
 10: if split attribute is categorical then
 11: for i = 1 to n do
 12: Create_Decision_Tree_Componendo_and_Dividendo(root, D_i)
 13: end for
 14: end if
 15: if split attribute is numerical then
 16: for i = 1 to 2 do
 17: Create-Decision-Tree(root, D_i)
 18: end for
 19: end if
 20: Find_Classification_Accuracy(root)

Algorithm-3 Find_Good_Split_Attribute_Componendo_and_Dividendo(root, D)

1:for each attribute i in the attribute list do
 2: if attribute is categorical then
 3: attribute split score[i] = $\frac{x_1-y_1}{x_1+y_1} + \frac{x_2-y_2}{x_2+y_2} + \dots + \frac{x_n-y_n}{x_n+y_n}$
 4: end if
 5: else if attribute is numerical then
 6: attribute split score[i] = $\frac{x_1-y_1}{x_1+y_1} + \frac{x_2-y_2}{x_2+y_2}$
 7: end if
 8:select attribute whose attribute split score[i] is maximum
 9: return the selected good attribute

 Line-1: simply finds the homogeneity score value of the current node
 Lines-2,3,4: if all tuples in the root node have the same class label value, then current node is converted into leaf node and also appropriate class label is assigned to it and the execution flow returns back.
 Lines-5, 6, 7: if the attribute list is empty then the current node is converted into leaf node and then flow returns back.
 Line-8: finds the correct good split attribute.
 Line-9: divides the data in the current node into partitions with respect to the selected split attribute.
 Lines-10 to 14: for each individual partition of the selected categorical attribute, decision tree creation is recursively called.
 Lines-15 to 19: for numerical attributes decision tree creation is recursively called for left partition and right partition separately.
 Line-20: classification accuracy value of the decision tree model is determined by using selected test dataset.

 Categorical split attribute score = $\frac{x_1-y_1}{x_1+y_1} + \frac{x_2-y_2}{x_2+y_2} + \dots + \frac{x_n-y_n}{x_n+y_n}$ (1)

Where categorical attribute is divided into 'n' partitions, 1, 2, 3, 4,,n.

Numerical split attribute score = left partition componendo and dividendo + right partition componendo and dividendo

Numerical split attribute score = $\frac{x_1 - y_1}{x_1 + y_1} + \frac{x_2 - y_2}{x_2 + y_2}$

Data is separated into 'n' partitions with respect to the selected categorical split attribute but only two partitions for the selected numerical attributes.

Maximum class label count of the first partition-1 = x₁ and
 Minimum class label count of the first partition-1 = y₁ and
 Maximum class label count of the partition-n = x_n and
 Minimum class label count of the partition-n = y_n and

If x₁ = y₁ then partition-1 is said to be balanced partition; otherwise it is un-balanced partition. In general, split score is =
 Split value = combination of balanced splits and un-balanced splits. If x₁ = 65 and y₁=0 then partition score = $\frac{x_1-y_1}{x_1+y_1} = \frac{65-0}{65+0} = 1$,
 which indicates pure partition and it is always pure partitions are desirable. If all partitions are pure then attribute is pure;
 partition's maximum purity score is 1 and minimum purity score is 0.

TABLE-1 Sample Training Dataset, Employee_Dataset

S.no	Age	Qualification	Job_Category	Income	Happy
1	12	Ph.D	Teacher	Low	0
2	15	Ph.D	Teacher	Low	0
3	9	Ph.D	Professor	High	1
4	12	Ph.D	Professor	High	1
5	16	M.Tech	Teacher	Low	0
6	14	M.Tech	Teacher	Low	0
7	4	M.Tech	Teacher	Low	0
8	12	M.Tech	Lecturer	Medium	1
9	14	B.Tech	Lecturer	Medium	1
10	19	B.Tech	Lecturer	Medium	1
11	16	B.Tech	Lecturer	Medium	1
12	19	PDF	Professor	High	1
13	15	PDF	Professor	High	1
14	15	PDF	Professor	High	1

A simple hypothetical dataset called Employee_Dataset consisting of a set of 14 tuples, 9 of which have the class label 1 (positive class) and 5 of which have the class label 0 (negative class). The selected training dataset has one class label attribute with two distinct class labels and four input attributes, namely: age, qualification, job_category and income, here age is numerical attribute and the remaining attributes are categorical attributes. The dataset has two classes (1, 0). The categorical characteristics of qualification, job_category, and income respectively have corresponding distinct values of 4, 3, and 3. Tables 2, 3, 4, and 5 display the class label counts details of each attribute.

TABLE-2 class label counts of age numerical attribute

Attribute	Less than or equal <=	Greater than >	Less than or equal <= class counts		Greater than > class counts		Componendo and dividendo
			0	1	0	1	
age			0	1	0	1	
	age <=4	age >4	1	0	4	9	$(1 - 0)/(1 + 0) + (9 - 4)/(9 + 4) = 1.3846$
	age <=9	age >9	1	1	4	8	$(1 - 1)/(1 + 1) + (8 - 4)/(4 + 8) = 0.3333$
	age <=12	age >12	2	3	3	6	$(3 - 2)/(3 + 2) + (6 - 3)/(6 + 3) = 0.5333$
	age <=14	age >14	3	4	2	5	$(4 - 3)/(4 + 3) + (5 - 2)/(5 + 2) = 0.5714$
	age <=15	age >15	4	4	1	5	$(4 - 4)/(4 + 4) + (5 - 1)/(5 + 1) = 0.6667$
	age <=16	age >16	5	4	0	5	$(5 - 4)/(5 + 4) + (5 - 0)/(5 + 0) = 1.1111$
	age <=19	age >19	5	9	0	0	$(9 - 5)/(9 + 5) + (0 - 0)/(0 + 0) = 0.2857$

In the training dataset age attribute is a numerical attribute and its possible binary splits are shown in the TABLE-2. Optimal split value occurs at age <= 4 and age > 4. So, data in the current node is divided temporarily into two partitions such that all tuples whose age <= 4 are placed into left partition and all tuples whose age > 4 are placed in the right partition.

Normalized split score = $(1 - 0)/(1 + 0) + (9 - 4)/(9 + 4) = 1.3846$

TABLE-3 class label counts of Qualification categorical attribute

Qualification	Class-1	Class-0
PDF	3	0
Ph.D	2	2
M.Tech	1	3
B.Tech	3	0

Split score = $(3 - 0)/(3 + 0) + (2 - 2)/(2 + 2) + (3 - 1)/(3 + 1) + (3 - 0)/(3 + 0) = 1.0 + 0 + 0.5 + 1.0 = 2.5$

TABLE-4 class label counts of Job_Category categorical attribute

Job Category	Class-1	Class-0
Teacher	0	5
Lecturer	4	0
Professor	5	0

Split score = $(5 - 0)/(5 + 0) + (4 - 0)/(4 + 0) + (5 - 0)/(5 + 0) = 1.0 + 1.0 + 1.0 = 3.0$

TABLE-5 class label counts of Income categorical attribute

Income	Class-1	Class-0
Low	0	5
Medium	4	0
High	5	0

Split score = $(5 - 0)/(5 + 0) + (4 - 0)/(4 + 0) + (5 - 0)/(5 + 0) = 1 + 1 + 1 = 3.0$. All 3 partitions are pure partitions and as a result of this job_category attribute is the best split attribute.

Attributes = (age, qualification, job_category, income)

Split scores of attributes = (1.3846,2.5,3.0,3.0), Highest split score = 3.0 for Job_Category attribute and is selected as a split attribute.

The categorical attribute, job_category, is the best split attribute at the root node, with the highest aggregate split score of 3.0, hence the data is then separated into three partitions corresponding to each distinct categorical values, lecturer, professor, and teacher of Job_Category attribute. All partitions are pure and further data classification is not required. The resulted decision tree model is shown in FIG-1. In general and in many real time applications the decision tree may grow up to 4 or 5 levels.

FIG-1 Decision tree for the sample training dataset, Employee

5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

23 real standard machine learning datasets are freely download for experimentation purposes. They are pre-processed in accordance with the necessary format and separated into training and testing datasets. TABLE-6 displays dataset descriptions, including the sizes of the training and test datasets as well as the quantity of numerical and categorical characteristics. Some datasets only have numerical qualities, while others only contain categorical attributes. The remaining datasets contain both numerical and categorical attributes.

TABLE-6 Description of selected Datasets

S.No	Datasets	Instances		Attributes		
		Train	Test	Categorical	Numerical	Classes
1	Iris	100	50	-----	4	3
2	Glass	161	53	-----	10	7
3	Iono sphere	264	87	-----	34	2
4	Car data	1296	432	6	-----	4
5	Balance scale	469	156	4	-----	3
6	Breast cancer	427	142	-----	30	2
7	Nursery	9720	3240	8	-----	5
8	Mush room	6093	2031	22	-----	2
9	Dermatology	275	91	34	-----	6
10	Hayes roth	132	28	4	-----	3
11	Spect heart	80	187	22	-----	2
12	Abalone	1567	522	1	7	3
13	Primary tumor	226	113	17	-----	19
14	Student entrance	666	666	11	-----	
15	Monks problem	124	432	6	-----	2
16	Lenses data	24	24	4	-----	3
17	Tic tac toe	958	958	9	-----	2
18	User knowledge	194	64	5	-----	4
19	Credit approval	518	172	9	6	2
20	Bank marketing	3391	1130	9	7	2
21	Statlog vehicle	745	101	-----	18	4
22	Leaf data	255	85	-----	15	36
23	Employee	14	14	3	1	2

Easy interpretation and achieving highly competitive experimental results is the main goal of modern research intention. All the UCI machine learning datasets are standard datasets and freely available for experimentation purpose. Some of the selected datasets are systematically preprocessed for convenience. Note that totally 22 machine learning datasets and selected one synthetic simple dataset are employed in the real experiments, and all datasets are collected from the standard real UCI machine learning repository. Each dataset is divided into training and testing datasets in the ratio of 3:1 approximately. The proposed decision tree model's classification accuracy is determined using the selected test dataset; while the decision tree model is trained using the training dataset and test dataset is used for testing purpose. Many experiments are conducted using both C4.5 classifier model

(WEKA) as well using gradient boosting algorithm called XGBoost, and also using proposed Componendo and Dividendo (CAD) split attribute rule in experimentation. Now-a-days many research experts are being conducted varieties researches using large language models (LLMs) without actually using training step of the model construction.

TABLE-7 Existing C4.5 based data classification experimental (WEKA) results

sno	Dataset	Existing C4.5-Weka tool				Random forest accuracy
		accuracy	height	Leafs	Size	
1	Iris	92.0	5	5	9	96
2	Glass	96.2264	5	6	11	96.2264
3	Iono sphere	85.0575	10	15	29	93.1034
4	Car data	92.5926	6	121	170	93.287
5	Balance scale	76.9231	4	33	41	87.8205
6	Breast cancer	94.3662	6	10	19	97.1831
7	Nursery	97.1605	8	353	500	96.2346
8	Mush room	100.0	6	25	30	100.0
9	Dermatology	89.011	7	18	25	97.8022
10	Hayes roth	92.8571	4	19	25	85.7143
11	Spect heart	66.8449	5	5	9	68.4492
12	Abalone	58.8123	15	159	311	62.6437
13	Primary tumour	40.708	12	38	70	37.1681
14	Student entrance	66.3664	1	1	1	93.8438
15	Monks problem	75.6944	4	12	18	91.4352
16	Lenses data	91.6667	4	4	7	100.0
17	Tic tac toe	93.737	7	95	142	100.0
18	User knowledge	90.625	7	12	23	92.1875
19	Credit approval	84.8837	8	17	30	87.2093
20	Bank marketing	91.5929	9	78	113	91.1504
21	Statlog vehicle	68.8679	19	58	115	72.6415
22	Leaf data	62.3529	12	50	99	72.9412
23	Employee	100.00	1.0	1.0	1.0	100.00

Experimental results with C4.5 are shown in TABLE-7. Random forest results are shown only for understanding purpose. Classification accuracy (40.708) of primary tumour is very low, Statlog Vehicle and leaf data sets are moderately high and all the remaining classification accuracies are highly preferable and very good.

TABLE-8 Existing XGBoost based Experimental Results

Sno	Dataset	XGBoost CLASSIFICATION RESULTS				Height	leafs	size
		accuracy	precision	recall	F1-score			
1	Iris	92.00	0.9207	0.92	0.9187	3	5	9
2	Glass	98.11	0.9849	0.9811	0.9880	2	5	9
3	Iono sphere	89.66	0.8955	0.8966	0.8959	5	12	23
4	Car data	94.68	0.9496	0.9468	0.9460	5	29	57
5	Balance scale	82.60	0.8560	0.8260	0.8360	5	110	130
6	Breast cancer	97.18	0.9720	0.9718	0.9717	4	12	23
7	Nursery	99.78	0.9975	0.9978	0.9977	5	60	119
8	Mush room	100.0	1.000	1.000	1.000	5	19	37
9	Dermatology	96.70	0.9670	0.9670	0.9670	5	19	25
10	Hayes Roth	85.71	0.8655	0.8571	0.8568	5	17	33
11	Spect heart	65.78	0.6563	0.6578	0.6521	5	9	17
12	Abalone	60.92	0.6078	0.6092	0.6079	5	50	59
13	Primary tumour	43.36	0.4411	0.4336	0.4319	5	20	39
14	Student entrance	93.69	0.9372	0.9369	0.9355	5	43	85
15	Monks problem	97.22	0.9737	0.9722	0.9722	5	12	23
16	Lenses data	100.0	1.000	1.000	1.000	2	4	7
17	Tic tac toe	100.0	1.000	1.000	1.000	5	39	77
18	User knowledge	92.0	0.9251	0.9219	0.9184	5	11	21
19	Credit approval	84.30	0.8512	0.8430	0.8437	5	25	49
20	Bank marketing	90.44	0.8952	0.9044	0.8989	5	43	85
21	Statlog vehicle	99.0	1.000	1.000	1.000	3	3	5
22	Leaf data	77.65	0.5719	0.6000	0.57580	9	24	47
23	Employee	100.00	1.0	1.0	1.0	2	3	4

XGBoost(extreme gradient boosting) algorithm is scalable and highly efficient and it is widely used in many machine learning applications. Working principle of XGBoost is based on gradient boosting, which creates ensemble of decision tree models one after another. Experimental results of XGBoost technique are shown in TABLE-8. Experimental results of XGBoost are almost good in the case of all the selected training and testing datasets.

Experimental results of the proposed Componendo and Dividendo (CAD) split attribute technique are presented in the TABLE-9. In majority of the cases experimental results of the proposed Componendo and Dividendo (CAD) split attribute technique are superior and these are highly desirable for many of the real time applications including medical data, business, agriculture and retail. Various parameter values are shown and these values are useful for comparison purpose. In the proposed method, the size

and the number of leaf nodes is very high only in the case of Nursery dataset but in all other datasets all parameter values are small and simple. It is a known fact that XGBoost is a potential efficient machine learning technique in terms of scalability, classification accuracy and speed.

TABLE-9 Proposed data split technique, Componendo and Dividendo, based Experimental Results

Rid	Dataset	PROPOSED COMPONENDO AND DIVIDENDO SPLIT ATTRIBUTE RULE						
		Accuracy	precision	recall	F1-score	Height	leafs	size
1	Iris	99.99	0.9999	0.9999	0.9999	4	4	7
2	Glass	99.99	0.8333	0.8333	0.8333	82	82	163
3	Iono sphere	99.99	0.9999	0.9999	0.9999	2	2	3
4	Car data	83.06	0.9507	0.5983	0.6880	5	55	74
5	Balance scale	89.74	0.5000	0.5000	0.5000	3	25	31
6	Breast cancer	99.99	0.9999	0.9999	0.9999	2	2	3
7	Nursery	95.74	0.9773	0.9731	0.9739	8	1370	2202
8	Mush room	100.0	0.9995	0.9995	0.9995	7	24	30
9	Dermatology	60.44	0.7396	0.5423	0.5691	5	18	24
10	Hayes roth	92.86	0.6667	0.6154	0.6389	4	19	25
11	Spect heart	69.23	0.8230	0.6491	0.6222	3	3	5
12	Abalone	67.43	0.5010	0.6667	0.5564	2	2	3
13	Primary tumour	44.25	0.3519	0.1736	0.1909	9	20	34
14	Student entrance	99.99	1.0	1.0	1.0	3	3	5
15	Monks problem	96.30	0.9655	0.9629	0.9630	7	41	63
16	Lenses data	100.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	5	21	39
17	Tic tac toe	100.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	8	243	379
18	User knowledge	100.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	6	6	11
19	Credit approval	98.84	0.9899	0.9867	0.9881	2	2	3
20	Bank marketing	90.27	0.9512	0.5175	0.5082	5	84	94
21	Statlog vehicle	99.99	0.9999	0.9999	0.9999	3	3	5
22	Leaf data	80.00	0.6750	0.7000	0.6800	21	112	223
23	Employee	100.00	1.0	1.0	1.0	2	3	4

TABLE-10 Comparison of classification accuracies of Random forest C4.5, XGBOOST and Componendo and Dividendo rule

S.no	Dataset Name	Random forest accuracy	C4.5 accuracy	XGBoost accuracy	Proposed Componendo and Dividendo split rule
1	Iris	96	92.0	92.00	99.99
2	Glass	96.2264	96.2264	98.11	99.99
3	Iono sphere	93.1034	85.0575	89.66	99.99
4	Car data	93.287	92.5926	94.68	83.06
5	Balance scale	87.8205	76.9231	82.60	89.74
6	Breast cancer	97.1831	94.3662	97.18	99.99
7	Nursery	96.2346	97.1605	99.78	95.74
8	Mush room	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0
9	Dermatology	97.8022	89.011	96.70	60.44
10	Hayes Roth	85.7143	92.8571	85.71	92.86
11	Spect heart	68.4492	66.8449	65.78	69.23
12	Abalone	62.6437	58.8123	60.92	67.43
13	Primary tumour	37.1681	40.708	43.36	44.25
14	Student entrance	93.8438	66.3664	93.69	99.99
15	Monks problem	91.4352	75.6944	97.22	96.30
16	Lenses data	100.0	91.6667	100.0	100.0
17	Tic tack toe	100.0	93.737	100.0	100.0
18	User knowledge	92.1875	90.625	92.0	100.0
19	Credit approval	87.2093	84.8837	84.30	98.84
20	Bank marketing	91.1504	91.5929	90.44	90.27
21	Statlog vehicle	72.6415	68.8679	74.06	99.99
22	Leaf data	72.9412	62.3529	77.65	80.00
23	Employee	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00

Comparisons of classification accuracy details are shown in the TABLE-10. The suggested or selected or proposed Componendo and dividendorule approach is superior in fourteen datasets, proposed method is equal to XGBoost in four datasets and XGBoost is superior only in two datasets and C4.5 is superior in only two datasets and finally random forest is superior only in one dataset.. Therefore, the proposed (in this paper) Componendo and dividendo split attribute technique that is suggested in this work is very much better than the earlier split point techniques that are already in use. Earlier it was thought that the random forest algorithm, the greatest classification algorithm ever, has classification accuracy that is even higher than some of the others.

RANDOM FOREST ALGORITHM

The Random Forest algorithm, a group of decision trees known as ensemble classifiers, is a well-liked and effective algorithm. It is regarded solely as a representative classifier due to its high classification accuracy and non-comparability with other algorithms.

However, some of the latest classifiers can outperform random forests in terms of classification accuracy. Generally speaking, we just examine, evaluate, and contrast other classification algorithms including many state-of-the-art decision tree construction techniques—not the random forest. In many cases, random forest algorithm produces high predictive results.

TABLE-11 Comparison of classification tree heights of C4.5, XGBoost and Componendo and Componendo and Dividendo rule

S.no	Dataset Name	C4.5 decision tree height	XGBoost decision tree height	Proposed Componendo and Dividendo rule height
1	Iris	5	5	3
2	Glass	5	5	6
3	Iono sphere	10	8	2
4	Car data	6	6	6
5	Balance scale	4	4	4
6	Breast cancer	6	6	2
7	Nursery	8	8	7
8	Mush room	6	6	5
9	Dermatology	7	7	7
10	Hayes roth	4	7	4
11	Spect heart	5	4	3
12	Abalone	15	10	3
13	Primary tumour	12	12	7
14	Student entrance	1	1	1
15	Monks problem	4	4	4
16	Lenses data	4	3	4
17	Tic tac toe	7	7	7
18	User knowledge	7	7	3
19	Credit approval	8	8	8
20	Bank marketing	9	9	9
21	Statlog vehicle	19	11	4
22	Leaf data	12	12	12
23	Employee	2	2	2

Decision Tree heights comparison details are shown in the TABLE-11. In all the cases except in the case of Lenses data, proposed Componendo and dividendo split technique is very good and have sub-optimal heights, which are far better than the other methods.

CONCLUSIONS

Decision tree learning is crucial in many applications including medical, business, agriculture, government, transportation and so on. During decision tree creation selecting the good split attribute is even more important in selecting and using good mathematical formula based metric. In the present research paper an excellent new split attribute technique called Componendo and Dividendo (CAD) rule is proposed. The performance of CAD is experimentally verified using standard datasets and it has been observed that CAD out performs all the existing decision tree classifier models including C4.5, Random Forest and XGBoost algorithms. In the future additional extra steps will be thoroughly analyzed, enhanced in multitude ways and applied for the improvement of proposed Componendo and Dividendo data split attribute rule in decision tree learning.

REFERENCES

- [1] J. R. Quinlan, "Induction of decision trees," Machine Learning., vol. 1, pp. 81–106, 1986.
- [2] Ibomoiye Domor Mieny, and Nobert Jere, "A Survey of Decision Trees: Concepts, Algorithms, and Applications", Received 26 May 2024, accepted 17 June 2024, date of publication 19 June 2024, date of current version 27 June 2024. Digital Object Identifier 10.1109/ACCESS.2024.3416838, IEEE Access
- [3] Candice Bentejac, Anna Csorgo, "A Comparative Analysis of XGBoost", November 2019, DOI: [10.48550/arXiv.1911.01914](https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.1911.01914)
- [4] Zengyou He, Ziyao Wu, Guangyao. Xu, Yan. Liu and QuanZou, "Decision Tree for sequences", IEEE Transactions on Knowledge and Data Engineering, Vol.35, No. 1, January 2023.
- [5] H. Liu, M. Cocea, "Induction of classification rules by Gini-index based rule generation", Information Sciences, Volumes 436–437, April 2018, Pages 227-246, ELSEVIER,
- [6] K. Muata, O. Bryson and K. Giles, "Splitting methods for decision tree induction: An exploration of the relative performance of two entropy-based families", published July 2006, volume 8, pages 195-209,
- [7] Xu Linzhang, ; Zhao Qiang; Zhang Yanning, "A New Structuring Method of Decision Tree", Published in: 2008 International Conference on Computer and Electrical Engineering, Date of Conference: 20-22 December 2008, Date Added to IEEE Xplore: 09 January 2009, Print ISBN:978-0-7695-3504-3, DOI: 10.1109/ICCEE.2008.50
- [8] Laviniu Aurelian Badulescu, "A Chi-Square Based Splitting Criterion Better for the Decision Tree Algorithms", October 2021, DOI:10.1109/ICSTCC52150.2021.9607285, Conference: 2021 25th International Conference on System Theory, Control and Computing (ICSTCC)
- [9] Yisen Wang, Chaobing Song and Shu-Tao Xia, "Unifying the Split Criteria of Decision Trees Using Tsallis Entropy", arXiv:1511.08136v5 [stat.ML] 23 Aug 2016
- [10] Maciej Jaworski, Piotr Duda, Leszek Rutkowski, "New splitting criteria for decision trees in stationary data streams", ACCEPTED FOR PUBLICATION IN Volume 31, Issue 7, 2025

- IEEE TRANSACTIONS ON NEURAL NETWORKS AND LEARNING SYSTEM, This work was supported by the Polish National Science Center under Grant No. 2014/15/B/ST7/05264
- [11] D. Mabuni, S. AquterBabu, C. Sudarsana Reddy, "A Novel Direct Formula Based Technique for Predicting the Class Label New Unseen Test Tuple without Learning", Publisher IEEE, Published in 2024 International Conference on Emerging Techniques in Computational Intelligence.
- [12] I domorMienie and N. Jere, "A Survey of Decision Trees: Concepts, Algorithms, and Applications", Published in: IEEE Access (Volume: 12), DOI: 10.1109/ACCESS.2024.3416838, Date of Publication: 19 June 2024
- [13] S. Calzavara, C. Lucchese, G. Tolomei, S. Assefa, and S. Orlando, "Treant: Training evasion aware decision trees", September 2020, Data Mining and Knowledge Discovery 34(1-4), DOI:10.1007/s10618-020-00694-9.
- [14] M. FlorinaBalcan and Dravyansh Sharma, "Learning Accurate and Interpretable Decision Trees", Published: 26 Apr 2024, Last Modified: 15 Jul 2024
- [15] E. Demirović, A. Lukina, E. Jeffrey Chan, James Bailey, Christopher Leckie, Kotagiri Ramamohanarao, Peter J. Stuckey "MurTree: Optimal Classification Trees via Dynamic Programming and Search", The Journal of Machine Learning Research, Volume 23, Issue 1, Article No.: 26, Pages 1169 – 1215, Published: 01 January 2022 Publication History
- [16] Mohammad Norouzi, Maxwell Collins, Matthew A Johnson, David J Fleet, Pushmeet Kohli, "Efficient Non-greedy Optimization of Decision Trees", NIPS'15: Proceedings of the 29th International Conference on Neural Information Processing Systems - Volume 1, Pages 1729 - 1737
- [17] Mohammad Arifuzzaman, Md. Rakibul Hasan, Tasnia Jahan Toma, Samia Binta Hassan and Anup Kumar Paul, "An Advanced Decision Tree-Based Deep Neural Network in Nonlinear Data Classification", Technologies 2023, 11(1), 24; <https://doi.org/10.3390/technologies11010024>, MDPI.
- [18] Rodrigo C. Barros, André C. P. L. F. de Carvalho & Alex A. Freitas, "Head-Dt: Automatic Design of Decision Tree Algorithms", first online 01-jan-2015, pp 59-76.
- [19] Anna Atramentov, Hector Leiva and Vasant Honavar, "A Multi-relational Decision Tree Learning Algorithm – Implementation and Experiments", International Conference on Inductive Logic Programming, International Conference on Inductive Logic Programming
- [20] Vasiliki Matzavela, Efthymios Alepis, "Decision tree learning through a Predictive Model for Student Academic Performance in Intelligent M-Learning environments", Computers and Education: Artificial Intelligence, Volume 2, 2021, 100035
- [21] Zengyou He; Ziyao Wu; Guangyao Xu; Yan Liu; Quan Zou, "Decision Trees for Sequences", Published in: IEEE Transactions on Knowledge and Data Engineering (Volume: 35, Issue: 1, 01 January 2023)
- [22] Gabriele Tolomei; Fabrizio Silvestri, "Generating Actionable Interpretations from Ensembles of Decision Trees", Published in: IEEE Transactions on Knowledge and Data Engineering (Volume: 33, Issue: 4, 01 April 2021), Page(s): 1540 – 1553, Date of Publication: 04 October 2019, DOI: 10.1109/TKDE.2019.2945326
- [23] Smith Tsang, Ben Kao; Kevin Y. Yip; Wai-Shing Ho; Sau Dan Lee, "Decision Trees for Uncertain Data", Published in: IEEE Transactions on Knowledge and Data Engineering (Volume: 23, Issue: 1, January 2011), Page(s): 64 – 78, Date of Publication: 21 August 2009, DOI: 10.1109/TKDE.2009.175
- [24] Pui Kuen Fong; Jens H. Weber-Jahnke, "Privacy Preserving Decision Tree Learning Using Unrealized Data Sets", Published in: IEEE Transactions on Knowledge and Data Engineering (Volume: 24, Issue: 2, February 2012), Page(s): 353 – 364, Date of Publication: 09 November 2010, DOI: 10.1109/TKDE.2010.226
- [25] Kuan-Hsun Chen, Chiahui Su, Christian Hakert, Sebastian Buschjäger, Chao-Lin Lee, Jenq Kuen Lee, Katharina Morik, Jian-Jia Chen, "Efficient Realization of Decision Trees for Real-Time Inference", ACM Transactions on Embedded Computing Systems, Volume 21, Issue 6, Article No.: 68, Pages 1 – 26, <https://doi.org/10.1145/3508019>, Published: 18 October 2022 Publication History
- [26] F. Aaboub, H. Chamial, T. Ouaderhman, "Statistical analysis of various splitting criteria for decision trees", October 2023, Journal of Algorithms & Computational Technology 17, October 2023 Journal of Algorithms & Computational Technology 17, DOI:10.1177/17483026231198181
- [27] J. M. Luna, "Building more accurate decision trees with the additive tree," , *Proc. Nat. Acad. Sci. USA*, vol. 116, no. 40, pp. 19887–19893, 2019.
- [28] Y. Qian, H. Xu, J. Liang, B. Liu, J. Wang, "Fusing Monotonic Decision Trees", Published in: IEEE Transactions on Knowledge and Data Engineering (Volume: 27, Issue: 10, 01 October 2015), Page(s): 2717 – 2728, DOI: 10.1109/TKDE.2015.2429133
- [29] David W. Jin, Xiang Zhang, S. Vosoughi, "Zero-Shot Decision Tree Construction via Large Language Models", DOI: <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2501.16.247>